

(*Pyricularia oryzae*) are major diseases. BB inflicts heavy losses every year.

During 1984-85 kharif, we screened 103 entries for BB resistance under natural disease pressure in Navsari and Vyara. Each entry was transplanted in 2 rows, each 2.25 × 0.3 m. One row of highly susceptible GR11 was transplanted between each entry and on all sides. Fertilizer was applied at 150-75-0 kg NPK/ha. At 40 d after transplanting, the entries were inoculated by clipping the leaf tips and spraying a bacterial suspension collected

from naturally infected leaves. Disease severity was rated on the *Standard evaluation system for rice*, 15 d after inoculation.

Variation in disease intensity in the two locations may be due to variation in the pathogen as well as differences in disease pressure (see table). Of the 103 entries screened, none were resistant, only 4 were moderately resistant (IRTP8160, IRTP10492, IRTP12158, and 3-8-3-3-1), and 23 scored 5 at both sites. □

Screening of rice cultures against BB under natural conditions. Navsari, India, 1984-85 kharif.

BB score	Entries (no.)		Entries (no.) common at both locations
	Navsari	Vyara	
1	1	—	—
3	15	19	4
5	51	54	23
7	29	29	6
9	7	1	—
Total	103	103	

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization INSECT RESISTANCE

Reaction of rice varieties to the mite *Oligonychus oryzae*

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A sudden and severe incidence of *O. oryzae* occurred the first week of Sep 1986 at RRS, when maximum temperature shot up to 36 °C. Mites inhabited the underside of the rice lamina in the nursery as well as in the

main fields. Affected plants showed whitish patches on leaf surfaces; in severe cases, the leaves turned grayish white and dried up.

Severe incidence also occurred in *Echinochloa colona*, a wetland weed found with rice that may be an alternate host.

Fifteen Tamil Nadu and 8 IRRI varieties being raised in nonrandomized observational plots (10 m²) were screened for reaction to mite. The crops

were at the booting to heading stage. Population/cm² was measured by selecting 2 leaves from random hills and counting mites on a cm² area. For percent leaf area affected, leaves were selected from 5 random hills and affected and unaffected portions measured.

Most of the Tamil Nadu varieties had no mite incidence (see table). IRRI varieties were affected, particularly IR62. □

Reaction of rice varieties to mite incidence in Tamil Nadu, India, 1986.

Variety	Origin	Mites/cm ²	Leaf damage (%)
TM8089	Tamil Nadu	0	0
TKM9	Tamil Nadu	0	0
TNAU80058	Tamil Nadu	0	0
CO 41	Tamil Nadu	0	0
ACM10	Tamil Nadu	0	0
ACM9	Tamil Nadu	0	0
AD85001	Tamil Nadu	0	0
AD9246	Tamil Nadu	0	0
ADT36	Tamil Nadu	0	0
IR60	IRRI	1	3
IR30	IRRI	1	5
AD24417	Tamil Nadu	2	5
AD25723	Tamil Nadu	2	6
PY3	Tamil Nadu	3	2
IR56	IRRI	6	15
IR52	IRRI	6	21
IR64	IRRI	6	21
ADT31	Tamil Nadu	6	22
IR50	IRRI	10	24
IR58	IRRI	10	28
TPS1	Tamil Nadu	15	60
CO 39	Tamil Nadu	15	60
IR62	IRRI	20	100

Resistance to whitebacked planthopper (WBPH) in Rajasthan

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WBPH was found for the first time in Rajasthan during the 1986 wet season. The infestation began the first week of Sep, infested varieties began showing hopperburn patches in late Sep.

We evaluated resistance in the field of 30 varieties from the Uniform Varietal Trial early group and 20 varieties from the advanced trial. Varieties were grown in a randomized block design at 20- × 15-cm spacing with 3 replications. Scoring according to the *Standard evaluation system for rice* was in the last week of Oct.